

1 **Therapeutic targeting in colorectal cancer for the treatment of the primary tumor: NAT10.**

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6 Colorectal cancer results in nearly 1,000,000 deaths each year (1-5). We recently utilized whole
7 transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and
8 phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8).
9 Measuring total transcription with RNA-sequencing and microarray in cancer and the normal tissues from
10 which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel chemotherapies with optimized
11 therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (10, 11) to measure total
12 transcription in the primary tumors of humans with colorectal cancer. We describe a therapeutic target
13 that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in humans with colorectal cancer, *NAT10*, as a candidate
14 therapeutic target for the medical management of the primary tumor in colorectal cancer.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in primary tumors of the large intestine (colon and rectum) to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the colorectal cancer transcriptome in humans: a therapeutic target that is differentially expressed and up-regulated, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: NAT10.

Results

Figure 1: NAT10 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=5 normal tissue from the colon/rectum (human)
n=5 primary tumors of the colon/rectum (human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55226	1.96E-15	0.212	-7.943538	-1.6875313	1252.51	NAT10	284/22047	98.7

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors in humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *NAT10* in colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of NAT10 changed more than 98% of the human colorectal cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,047 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NAT10 messenger RNA in colorectal cancer (CRC), demonstrating up-regulation of NAT10 during transformation in CRC.

II. Primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=2 normal tissue from the colon/rectum (human)
n=2 primary tumors of the colon/rectum (human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55226	8.79E-03	0.493	-2.6201051	-1.292876	1125.07	NAT10	1855/19664	90.6

Through measurement of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to normal colorectal tissue, we validated differential expression of NAT10 in CRC in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of NAT10 here changed more than 90% of the colorectal cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,664 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NAT10 messenger RNA in the primary tumor of humans with colorectal cancer, demonstrating up-regulation of NAT10 during transformation in CRC.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of NAT10 defines the tumor transcriptome in human
2 colorectal cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of NAT10, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
7 efficacy in patients with colorectal cancer who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying
8 the most effective first-line chemotherapy regimens for humans with colorectal cancer, as well as for
9 patients with disease recurrence at the primary site. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with
10 chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at
11 anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is
12 most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (12).
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References

1. Kuipers, E.J., Grady, W.M., Lieberman, D., Seufferlein, T., Sung, J.J., Boelens, P.G., van de Velde, C.J. and Watanabe, T., 2015. Colorectal cancer. *Nature reviews. Disease primers*, 1, p.15065.
2. Arnold, M., Sierra, M.S., Laversanne, M., Soerjomataram, I., Jemal, A. and Bray, F., 2017. Global patterns and trends in colorectal cancer incidence and mortality. *Gut*, 66(4), pp.683-691.
3. Dekker, E., Tanis, P.J., Vleugels, J.L., Kasi, P.M. and Wallace, M.B., 2019. Colorectal cancer. *The Lancet*, 394(10207), pp.1467-1480.
4. Keum, NaNa, and Edward Giovannucci. "Global burden of colorectal cancer: emerging trends, risk factors and prevention strategies." *Nature reviews Gastroenterology & hepatology* 16, no. 12 (2019): 713-732.
5. Ferlay, J., Shin, H.R., Bray, F., Forman, D., Mathers, C. and Parkin, D.M., 2010. Estimates of worldwide burden of cancer in 2008: GLOBOCAN 2008. *International journal of cancer*, 127(12), pp.2893-2917.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
10. GSE143939: GSE143939. The First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University. Zhengzhou, China. January 18, 2023.
11. GSE200427:: Jiang, Y., Wang, X., Li, L., He, J., Jin, Q., Long, D., Liu, C., Zhou, W. and Liu, K., 2022. A systematic analysis of C5ORF46 in gastrointestinal tumors as a potential prognostic and immunological biomarker. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 13, p.926943.
12. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE143939 and GSE200427 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors of the colon and normal tissue from the colon using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.